

A Theoretical Review on Cultural Ecosystem Services and Visitor Management in Protected Areas

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Abstract

Protected areas play a crucial role not only in biodiversity conservation but also in enhancing human well-being through cultural ecosystem services (CES). CES encompass non-material benefits that arise from people's interactions with nature, including aesthetic, spiritual, recreational, educational, and social values. This article provides a theoretical overview of the evolution and classification of CES, focusing on their psychological and societal significance. Drawing on both national and international case studies, the article discusses how CES are perceived, valued, and integrated into visitor management strategies in protected areas. The findings highlight that CES contribute not only to conservation goals but also to sustainable tourism, environmental education, and social cohesion. Accordingly, this review aims to raise awareness about the necessity of incorporating CES into the effective planning and management of protected areas.

Keywords: Cultural ecosystem services, visitor management, protected areas, nature connectedness, spatial equity.

Korunan Alanlarda Kültürel Ekosistem Hizmetleri ve Ziyaretçi Yönetimi Üzerine Literatür İncelemesi

Öz

Korunan alanlar, yalnızca biyolojik çeşitliliğin korunması açısından değil, aynı zamanda topluma sundukları kültürel ekosistem hizmetleri (KEH) ile insan refahı üzerinde derin etkiler yaratmaktadır. KEH, bireylerin doğayla kurduğu etkileşimler yoluyla estetik, manevi, sosyal, eğitsel ve rekreasyonel değerler üretmektedir. Bu çalışmada kültürel ekosistem hizmetleri kavramının tarihsel gelişimi, sınıflandırılması ve insan psikolojisi ile olan çok boyutlu ilişkisi teorik bir çerçevede ele alınmıştır. Ayrıca ulusal ve uluslararası çalışmalardan örnekler aracılığıyla korunan alanlarda kültürel hizmetlerin nasıl algılandığı, değerlendirildiği ve ziyaretçi yönetimiyle nasıl bütünleştirildiği tartışılmıştır. Bulgular, KEH'in yalnızca doğa koruma hedeflerine değil, aynı zamanda sürdürülebilir turizm, eğitim ve sosyal bütünleşmeye katkı sağladığını ortaya koymaktadır. Bu bağlamda çalışma, kültürel hizmetlerin daha etkin şekilde planlanması ve yönetilmesine yönelik bir farkındalık oluşturmayı hedeflemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kültürel ekosistem hizmetleri, ziyaretçi yönetimi, korunan alanlar, doğa ile bağ kurma, mekânsal adalet.

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1. Introduction

Throughout human history, interactions with nature have extended beyond merely fulfilling basic needs, significantly shaping individuals' cultural, aesthetic, and spiritual development. These multidimensional relationships reveal that the benefits provided by ecosystems are not solely material but also deeply cultural and emotional. In this regard, the concept of ecosystem services offers a systematic approach to assessing the contributions of nature to human well-being (Daily, 1997; Costanza et al., 1997; Boyd & Banzhaf, 2007; Kaya, 2019).

The concept gained widespread recognition following the publication of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) in 2005, which introduced a comprehensive classification of ecosystem services. According to the MEA, ecosystem services are divided into four main categories: provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural services. Among these, CES are characterized by their intangible nature and encompass spiritual connections with nature, recreational engagement, aesthetic appreciation, educational benefits, and the shaping of cultural identity

Protected areas, which combine high biodiversity with remarkable landscape value, are where cultural CES are most intensively experienced (Li et al., 2020). These areas provide opportunities for individuals to connect with nature and engage with cultural values both personally and socially. Activities such as hiking, swimming, and camping contribute not only to physical health but also to psychological well-being, social cohesion, and environmental awareness (Willis, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). Beyond these direct benefits, CES also play a significant role in supporting community identity, social integration, and the transmission of traditional knowledge. From an economic perspective, CES-related activities such as ecotourism and local service provision generate income and promote sustainable rural development (Roux et al., 2020).

Moreover, the sociological dimensions of CES are evident in the way these experiences support community identity and intergenerational knowledge transfer. From an economic perspective, CES-related activities in protected areas can generate income through ecotourism and local services, supporting sustainable rural development. Thus, addressing CES through a multi-dimensional lens strengthens the holistic understanding and management of protected areas (Roux et al., 2020).

However, the extent to which CES can be enjoyed is closely linked to the carrying capacity of protected areas and the efficacy of visitor management strategies. Excessive and unregulated visitor pressure threatens the sustainability of natural resources and diminishes the quality of cultural experiences (Newsome et al., 2012; Clements & Cumming, 2017). Therefore, managing CES effectively is critical not only for achieving conservation objectives but also for maintaining visitor satisfaction (Akten & Gül, 2014).

This study aims to explore the theoretical foundations of cultural ecosystem services, trace their conceptual evolution, and analyze their relationship with visitor management in protected areas. Through the examination of national and international case studies, this research evaluates the diversity and impact of CES applications and provides strategic recommendations aligned with sustainability principles.

1.1. Conceptual Development and Classification of Cultural Ecosystem Services

The concept of ecosystem services began to take shape in the 1970s when ecologists started to explore the linkages between human well-being and natural systems. Over the years, the term has evolved to encompass interdisciplinary dimensions, including environmental science, economics, sociology, and environmental policy. One of the seminal definitions was proposed by Daily (1997), who described ecosystem services as "the conditions and processes through which natural ecosystems sustain and fulfill human life." Similarly, Costanza et al. (1997) defined them as "the benefits humans derive from ecosystem functions," while De Groot et al. (2002) emphasized both the direct and indirect advantages provided by ecological structures and processes.

A major milestone in the systematization of the concept was the publication of the *Millennium Ecosystem Assessment* (MEA). The MEA offered a structured classification of ecosystem services into four main categories:

1. Provisioning Services – e.g., food, freshwater, raw materials;
2. Regulating Services – e.g., climate regulation, water purification, air quality;
3. Supporting Services – e.g., photosynthesis, soil formation, nutrient cycling;
4. Cultural Services – e.g., aesthetic appreciation, spiritual fulfillment, recreation, education, and cultural heritage.

Among these, CES stand out due to their non-material nature. While they do not produce physical goods, CES significantly influence how people perceive and interact with the natural world (MEA, 2005). These services include aesthetic, ethical, spiritual, educational, historical, and social dimensions of human–nature relationships.

While the categorization of CES varies slightly across the literature, the most commonly cited components include (MEA, 2005; Albayrak, 2012):

- Recreation and Ecotourism: Activities such as hiking, swimming, camping, and picnicking;
- Aesthetic Values: Visual quality and inspirational value of natural landscapes;
- Spiritual and Ethical Values: Sacred natural sites and spiritual bonds with nature;
- Cultural Heritage and Diversity: Historic sites, traditional land uses, and cultural symbols;
- Education and Knowledge Systems: Nature-based learning, environmental education, and scientific research;
- Social Cohesion and Sense of Place: Community bonding, identity, and place attachment;
- Inspiration and Creativity: Influence of nature on art, literature, music, and innovation.

The multidimensional nature of CES plays a key role not only in individual experiences but also in shaping collective cultural identities. People's perception and valuation of nature are shaped by factors such as geography, culture, and socio-economic background (Daniel et al., 2012). Therefore, assessments of CES should incorporate both objective indicators and subjective, context-specific factors.

A deeper understanding of CES contributes significantly to fields such as conservation policy, environmental education, and sustainable tourism. In this regard, CES function as a critical link between ecological systems and human well-being, promoting a holistic approach to sustainability (MEA, 2005).

1.2. Visitor Management

Ensuring the sustainability of CES within protected areas requires the effective management of visitor flow and behavior. Visitor management not only enhances the quality of the visitor experience but also plays a critical role in preserving ecological integrity and promoting the sustainable use of natural resources (Manning & Lime, 2000; Gökтуğ & Kurkut, 2016).

Visitor management encompasses a set of planned interventions and guidance strategies designed to safeguard both natural and cultural values. According to Manning and Lime (2000), these strategies can be broadly categorized into four main approaches:

1. Supply Management: Involves distributing visitor presence across time and space—e.g., directing visitors to less congested areas or off-peak periods—to reduce pressure on sensitive sites.
2. Demand Management: Focuses on regulating the number of visitors through mechanisms such as reservation systems, visitor quotas, and variable pricing schemes, thus avoiding surpassing the area's carrying capacity.

3. **Resource Management:** Aims to minimize ecological degradation through infrastructural improvements, regular maintenance, and ecologically sensitive regulations.
4. **Visitor Impact Management:** Involves influencing visitor behavior via information dissemination, environmental education, signage, guided tours, and—when necessary—direct enforcement.

Peterson and Lime (1979) further categorized these strategies into direct and indirect methods. Direct methods impose specific restrictions on visitor behavior (e.g., access limitations), while indirect methods aim to shape behavior through education, awareness campaigns, and interpretive programs that encourage voluntary compliance.

Therefore, visitor management is a key component in preserving the integrity of cultural ecosystem & depends on carefully planned use of protected areas with respect to time, space, and infrastructure. Equally important is guiding the nature–visitor interaction in a way that fosters respect and understanding (Göktuğ & Kurkut, 2016).

In their study on national parks, Göktuğ and Kurkut (2016) proposed a set of tools for sustainable visitor management that includes:

- Group size limitations,
- Zoning of activity areas,
- Seasonal access restrictions,
- Reservation and lottery systems,
- Establishment of visitor centers and environmental education programs,
- Use of digital navigation tools,
- Certification schemes, and
- Guided interpretation services.

The integration of technological tools such as social media monitoring, spatial analysis, and digital guidance platforms has also enhanced the ability to track visitor movements and behaviors in real time, leading to more adaptive and responsive management strategies (Göktuğ & Kurkut, 2016).

In this context, effective visitor management serves not only ecological objectives but also facilitates social outcomes, including the preservation of cultural landscapes, community participation, and the advancement of environmental education and ecotourism. Thus, visitor management is essential for preserving both the ecological integrity and cultural functionality of protected areas.

1.3. Relationship between Cultural Ecosystem Services and Visitor Management in Protected Areas

Protected areas hold strategic importance for the sustainable preservation of natural resources and their transfer to future generations. However, their significance extends beyond biodiversity conservation, as they also serve as spaces for human–nature interaction across cultural, spiritual, and emotional dimensions (Gül et al., 2006) . In this context, CES have become an increasingly integral consideration in the management of protected areas (Palomo et al., 2014).

The expression of CES in protected areas manifests through various non-material benefits, including nature-based recreation, educational experiences, cultural heritage preservation, spiritual fulfillment, creative inspiration, social interaction, and environmental awareness. Activities such as hiking, birdwatching, swimming, camping, and meditation enhance not only physical health but also mental well-being and social cohesion (Willis, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). These experiences often promote conservation-minded behaviors by increasing emotional attachment to nature (Zhang et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, the realization of such benefits is contingent upon multiple interrelated factors, including ecological carrying capacity, physical accessibility, the adequacy of supporting infrastructure, and, critically, the effectiveness of visitor management. Visitor behavior within protected areas exerts a direct influence on the quality, resilience, and long-term sustainability of CES. Unregulated or

unconscious use (manifested through practices such as off-trail hiking, improper waste disposal, disturbance of wildlife, and overcrowding in ecologically sensitive zones) can result in irreversible environmental degradation and a significant decline in service provision (Newsome et al., 2012).

Accordingly, there is a pressing need for the formulation and implementation of strategic management frameworks that are grounded in adaptive management principles, participatory planning processes, and empirically informed decision-making. These frameworks should aim to integrate conservation objectives with visitor engagement strategies, thereby ensuring the dual goals of ecological integrity and meaningful human-nature interaction are met in a balanced and sustainable manner.

The literature frequently highlights a relationship between CES and visitor satisfaction; however, the nature of this correlation often varies across studies. For instance, a multicenter quantitative study across several European countries conducted by Smith and Ram (2017), using survey-based Likert scale assessments, demonstrated a statistically significant positive correlation between landscape experiences and visitors' reported levels of spiritual, emotional, intellectual, and existential well-being.

Similarly, a case study by Arslan and Kaymaz (2020) in Türkiye's Gölcük Nature Park revealed a misalignment between the recreational services perceived by visitors and the park's long-term management strategies. This discrepancy underscores the need to better integrate CES dimensions into planning and policy frameworks to enhance both ecological and experiential outcomes.

Moreover, cultural ecosystem services can serve broader roles beyond conservation—such as reinforcing the continuity of cultural landscapes, connecting protected areas with local communities, and enhancing environmental education and sustainable tourism potential. In this regard, well-designed visitor management strategies become essential tools for preserving not just biodiversity but also the cultural and experiential dimensions of protected areas.

1.4. In-Depth Analysis with Selected Examples from National and International Studies

The assessment and integration of CES in protected areas are shaped by varying geographic, socio-cultural, and managerial contexts. Numerous studies in both national and international settings offer valuable insights into the methodologies, findings, and practical implications of CES-related research and applications.

For instance, Willis (2015), in a study conducted along England's Jurassic Coast, examined how tourism contributes to individual psychological well-being through CES. Using a mixed-methods approach—combining surveys, focus groups, and interviews—the study revealed that interaction with nature facilitated spiritual relaxation, mental rejuvenation, and emotional satisfaction. These intangible benefits were found to directly support both visitor satisfaction and long-term sustainability of the site.

Similarly, Smith and Ram (2017), in a survey conducted across eight European countries, evaluated cultural benefits through landscape experience. Their findings showed that visitors perceived profound spiritual, emotional, intellectual, and existential benefits. The study underscored the necessity of incorporating emotional and symbolic values into CES planning and policy development.

In the national context, Arslan and Kaymaz (2020) investigated visitor perceptions in Gölcük Nature Park, Türkiye. Their research highlighted a discrepancy between the CES perceived by visitors and the actual management plans.

This finding suggests that top-down planning approaches may overlook user needs and perceptions. As a result, the long-term sustainability of CES in the area could be at risk.

Jamean and Abas (2023) conducted a study in Malaysia's urban forests to assess visitor perceptions of CES and their willingness to pay for conservation. Results indicated that both regulatory and cultural services were highly valued, and visitors expressed strong support for voluntary financial contributions toward service maintenance.

In another case, Crouzat et al. (2022) performed a spatial analysis in three European mountain protected areas. Their study compared the potential supply and actual usage of CES and found a lack

of spatial overlap. Various factors were identified as contributing to the issue. Among these, accessibility, socio-cultural preferences, and land use patterns were particularly significant.

These factors underscore the importance of adopting management approaches that are both context-specific and participatory in nature.

Zhang et al. (2023) emphasized the influence of nature connection, spatial attachment, and participation in environmental events on pro-environmental behaviors. Their findings suggest that CES-based activities should be central to visitor engagement strategies.

Vasiljević et al. (2023) analyzed urban park use and determined that visitor motivations significantly varied by age, indicating the importance of considering sociodemographic variables in CES planning.

Pinheiro et al. (2021), in a study on marine protected areas in Brazil, explored how aesthetic values and social bonds shaped visitor preferences. Their findings called for the alignment of management strategies with user expectations regarding landscape beauty and social experience.

Clements and Cumming (2017) highlighted that safari- and nature-history-themed experiences in South African private protected areas were crucial for area sustainability, stressing that CES should be a core component of strategic conservation planning.

Palomo et al. (2014), in a Spanish context, questioned the effectiveness of rigid service-based zoning approaches and recommended flexible and adaptive management models that better accommodate CES.

Benetti and Langemeyer (2021), in their study in Italy's Circeo National Park, brought attention to inequities in CES access and associated spatial justice issues, indicating that marginalized groups often face barriers in benefitting from protected landscapes.

In a remote context, Li et al. (2020) studied the Qinghai–Tibet Plateau and concluded that biodiversity conservation and CES preservation must be pursued concurrently, especially in fragile ecosystems.

Pisani et al. (2021) examined how the economic valuation of CES can support protected area financing, providing a framework based on the case of Gargano National Park in Italy.

In the Po River Delta, Gaglio et al., (2023) demonstrated that integrating CES into governance processes enhances stakeholder engagement and participatory decision-making.

Finally, Martinez-Harms et al. (2018) revealed the effects of socioeconomic inequality on CES accessibility in Chile's biodiversity hotspots, while Niz et al. (2023) showed that CES, biodiversity, and habitat data can be combined using spatial tools to inform marine conservation decisions in Brazil.

These examples collectively demonstrate that integrating user-centered planning, spatial analysis, and social equity is not only beneficial but essential for developing effective and sustainable CES management strategies in protected areas.

2. Conclusion and Suggestions

This study aimed to holistically examine the role of CES in protected areas and their relationship with visitor management. CES represent the aesthetic, spiritual, educational, and recreational connections that individuals establish with nature. These non-material benefits not only support conservation objectives but also significantly enhance human well-being.

Rooted in ecological thought of the 1970s, the concept of ecosystem services gained greater structure and policy relevance with the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005), which formally recognized cultural services as one of the four main service categories. Since then, CES have been increasingly integrated into interdisciplinary frameworks concerned with sustainability, tourism, education, and public health.

Empirical studies conducted in protected areas worldwide consistently demonstrate that CES foster psychological well-being, emotional resilience, and pro-environmental behavior among visitors (Willis, 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). Recreational activities such as hiking, camping, and picnicking not only

improve physical health but also promote place attachment, environmental awareness, and sustainable behaviors—bridging the gap between conservation goals and societal benefits.

However, challenges remain in translating the value of CES into effective administrative and planning processes. For instance, Arslan and Kaymaz (2020) highlighted a mismatch between perceived services and long-term park management plans, while (Crouzat et al., 2022) noted a spatial disconnect between the potential supply and actual use of CES. These findings point to the limitations of top-down, biophysical-centered planning, and emphasize the need for more user-oriented, context-sensitive, and adaptive strategies.

Moreover, national and international case studies reveal that CES are shaped by local geographies, cultures, and socioeconomic structures. Aesthetic values, sense of place, and social experiences vary across regions, suggesting that CES-related policies should be developed using participatory, place-based, and flexible methodologies (Pinheiro et al., 2021; Clements & Cumming, 2017).

Although the current literature provides substantial insights into the value and functions of CES, there is still a relative scarcity of studies that explicitly address the nexus between CES and visitor management. Furthermore, methodological gaps exist in the measurement, spatial mapping, and user-based evaluation of CES. Therefore, future research should focus on developing multidisciplinary frameworks that incorporate stakeholder views, spatial-social datasets, and advanced tools for service monitoring and governance.

In conclusion, the effective management of CES not only ensures the protection of ecological resources but also enhances visitor satisfaction, environmental stewardship, and social sustainability. Integrating CES into decision-making processes systematically can lead to the multifunctional use of protected areas and a deeper harmony between human and ecological systems.

Future studies are encouraged to:

- Adopt multidisciplinary perspectives combining ecology, psychology, sociology, and planning;
- Utilize spatially explicit and participatory methods to evaluate CES distributions;
- Assess visitor perceptions and motivations in diverse contexts;
- Promote policy frameworks that integrate CES into the core of protected area governance;
- Address inequities in access to CES through inclusive and just planning approaches.

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As the study did not involve human or animal subjects, ethical committee approval was not required. The authors have diligently adhered to principles of academic integrity by properly citing all sources and avoiding any form of plagiarism or academic misconduct.

The data were interpreted with objectivity, and the research process was conducted in full compliance with the principles of academic honesty and the scientific method.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest

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